

Why did you engage with Thinking about how COVID-19 affected you?	What 3 words would you use to describe the experience?	What 3 words would you use to describe the support?
It was written into my course	Access to personal support	supportive, focused, helpful
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	Helpful, Targeted, Informative
To gain the post nominal	Discussions with other Faculty	Not attended the workshops
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	helpful useful
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	Helpful, Supportive, Invaluable
To reflect on my professional	Access to asynchronous learning	accessible, supportive, clear, practical, useful
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	The sessions were very helpful
To reflect on my professional	Access to asynchronous learning	Convenient, helpful, reassuring
It was written into my course	Access to personal support	I did not have any workshops
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	Drop-ins, guidance, encouragement
To develop my professional	Access to personal support	Supportive, Patiently, and Useful
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	Friendly, supportive and Useful-in-content, dense
To gain the post nominal	Discussions with other Faculty	Informative, thought-provoking
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	N/A - did not attend
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	Engaging, Creative and Motivational
To develop my professional	Access to personal support	Friendly, encouraging, motivating
To develop my professional	Access to personal support	encouraging; motivation useful; time-saving; referential
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	Useful, clarifying, friendly
To reflect on my professional	Online support events; Chat	I did not attend online workshops
To gain the post nominal	Access to asynchronous learning	Supportive Informative Motivational
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	Encouraging, Friendly, Comprehensive, Clear, Supportive
After a discussion with my	Access to personal support	supportive, focused, helpful
To gain the post nominal	Discussions with other Faculty	N/A Useful, supportive, flexible
To gain the post nominal	Access to asynchronous learning	Informative Friendly Helpful
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	Informative Supportive Reassuring
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	I was able to attend a workshop
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	helpful, supportive, reassuring
To reflect on my professional	Access to personal support	Practical, Insightful, Encouraging
To gain the post nominal	Online support events; Virtual	Foundation Building Drop Resourceful
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	Clear, Useful, Friendly Accessible, Detailed, Thorough
It was written into my course	Access to personal support	N/a detailed, straightforward
To progress my career;	Access to personal support	helpful; relevant; appropriate
To gain the post nominal	Access to asynchronous learning	useful available appropriate clear helpful wordy
After a discussion with my	Access to personal support	Supportive, 'you-centred' Accessible, comprehensive
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	personalised, non-threatening appropriate, straightforward
To gain the post nominal	Online support events; Discussion	Insightful, Supportive, Open
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	Informative; motivating; Clear; informative; thorough
To learn more about teaching	Access to personal support	Helpful, Informative and Helpful, Informative and
It was written into my course	Discussions with other Faculty	informative, supportive, essential, accessible, informative
To gain the post nominal	Access to personal support	I didn't make use of the Helpdesk

Increased my writing pro	Improved my understand	Allowed me to reflect or	Helped me to make futu
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Did not attend	Did not attend	Did not attend	Did not attend
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree
Disagree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Did not attend	Did not attend	Did not attend	Did not attend
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Did not attend	Did not attend	Did not attend	Did not attend
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Did not attend	Did not attend	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree
Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Did not attend	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Disagree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Did not attend	Did not attend	Did not attend	Did not attend

The asynchronous optio	Learnt about learning an	On a scale of 1-10 (with	It helped me to share pr
Agree	Agree	8	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	9	Strongly agree
Did not attend	Did not attend	10	Agree
Did not attend	Agree	8	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	10	Strongly agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	10	Agree
Agree	Disagree	8	Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	8	Agree
Did not attend	Strongly Agree	9	Agree
Agree	Agree	9	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	9	Agree
Agree	Disagree	8	Agree
Agree	Agree	5	Agree
Did not attend	Did not attend	5	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	10	Disagree
Agree	Agree	10	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	8	Strongly agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	9	Agree
Did not attend	Did not attend	1	Agree
Agree	Agree	8	Agree
Agree	Did not attend	7	Agree
Agree	Agree	8	Agree
Agree	Agree	8	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	10	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	10	Agree
Did not attend	Strongly Agree	10	Strongly agree
Strongly Agree	Did not attend	10	Agree
Agree	Agree	9	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	9	Agree
Agree	Disagree	7	Agree
Agree	Agree	8	Agree
Disagree	Disagree	8	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	5	Strongly Disagree
Agree	Agree	9	Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	8	Agree
Agree	Agree	8	Agree
Agree	Agree	10	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	8	Agree
Did not attend	Strongly Agree	9	Strongly agree
Did not attend	Did not attend	1	Strongly Disagree

Since completing Fellow Working with others thr I have altered my teachi The experience has mad			
Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Disagree	Agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Strongly agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly agree	Agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Agree
Strongly agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree
Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree
Strongly agree	Agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Strongly agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Agree
Agree	Strongly agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Agree
Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree
Strongly agree	Agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree
Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree
Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree
Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Agree
Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
Disagree	Agree	Agree	Disagree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree
Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree
Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree

Since completing Fellow	Have we increased a sen	Did you make any new c	Over the years we have
Online teaching	Yes	No	Challenging;Supportive;F
asked to present at Tilt S	Yes	Yes	Supportive;Valuable;Tra
Not yet engaged	Yes	Yes	Transformational;Collegi
Mentoring	Yes	Yes	Supportive;Valuable;
Becoming a HEA Reviewer	Yes	Yes	Challenging;Supportive;T
Obviously we've all had t	Yes	Yes	Supportive;Valuable;Tra
Publication and more cre	No	Yes	Supportive;Valuable;Pro
I have started to read mc	Yes	No	Supportive;Challenging;C
Collaborative work on m	Yes	Yes	Supportive;Valuable;Enj
Collaborative teaching ar	Yes	Yes	Supportive;Collaborative
I have participated in ET	Yes	Yes	Valuable;Enjoyable;Supp
Discussions with colleag	Yes	No	Valuable;Process-driven;
very little, just trying to s	No	No	Challenging;Supportive;V
Continued reflexivity as a	Yes	No	Supportive;Challenging;V
CreativeHE Jam, Twitter	Yes	Yes	Supportive;Enjoyable;Tra
Online moderation of un	Yes	Yes	Enjoyable;Valuable;Supp
Becoming an assessor	Yes	No	Challenging;Collaborative
TILTtalks	Yes	No	Challenging;Supportive;V
SCALE-UP and TBL pedag	Yes	No	Supportive;Valuable;Cha
Online webinars - compl	Yes	Yes	Challenging;Transformat
This fellowship has given	Yes	No	Supportive;Collegiate;Va
External webinars as a p	Yes	No	Enjoyable;Valuable;Pro
N/A	Yes	Yes	Supportive;Collegiate;Va
APA PGCERT	Yes	No	Challenging;Process-driv
N/A	Yes	Yes	Supportive;Valuable;Enj
Workshops within SST	Yes	No	Enjoyable;Supportive;Va
I've been trying to use a r	Yes	No	Valuable;Supportive;Pro
Thinking of applying for a	Yes	Yes	Supportive;Collegiate;Tra
Discussions with colleag	Yes	No	Challenging;Supportive;C
I have only recently com	Yes	Yes	Supportive;Valuable;Coll
None yet!	Yes	Yes	Supportive;Collaborative
MSTeams training	Yes	No	Challenging;Collegiate;C
None as been on annual	No	No	Process-driven;Just tickir
It wasn't that long ago, s	Yes	No	Challenging;Supportive;F
Supporting others with fr	Yes	Yes	Challenging;Supportive;C
I only completed a mont	Yes	No	Valuable;Supportive;Coll
I have taken more time t	Yes	No	Challenging;Valuable;Sup
I am more reflective on p	Yes	Yes	Challenging;Supportive;V
extensive reading, furthe	No	No	Burdensome;Challenging
None	No	No	Challenging;Process-driv

Would you recommend	How has your perception	Do you agree that Fellow	Which NTU resources are
Yes	yes	Agree	Workshops;Drop-in sessi
Yes	It hasn't really because I	Strongly agree	NOW Learning Room;Dro
Yes	NTU's team is supportive	Strongly agree	Fellowship stories;Suppo
Yes	Not sure that it has, but I	Agree	Drop-in sessions;Guides
Yes	It isn't as difficult as I first	Strongly agree	NOW Learning Room;Dro
Yes	Feels much less like a 'tic	Strongly agree	NOW Learning Room;Gu
Yes	Yes, indeed	Agree	MS Teams;NOW Learning
Yes	I was slightly concerned I	Agree	NOW Learning Room;Dro
Yes	I thought it would just be	Strongly agree	NOW Learning Room;Dro
Yes	Continue until I achieve i	Strongly Disagree	MS Teams;Drop-in sessio
Yes	At the beginning, I would	Strongly agree	Fellowship stories;
Yes	I understand the wider-s	Agree	NOW Learning Room;Dro
Yes	No	Agree	Workshops;Drop-in sessi
Yes	I learned a lot more about	Strongly agree	NOW Learning Room;MS
Yes	At the start, I was doing i	Strongly agree	MS Teams;Workshops;Su
Yes	N/a	Strongly agree	Workshops;Drop-in sessi
Yes	I have gained a better un	Strongly agree	Drop-in sessions;Worksh
Yes	In the beginning, I thoug	Strongly agree	Guides and Handbooks;D
Yes	I thought it was just a rec	Agree	MS Teams;NOW Learning
Yes	I did not anticipate the g	Strongly agree	Drop-in sessions;Guides
Yes	It hasn't	Agree	NOW Learning Room;MS
Yes	I've recognised that with	Agree	Guides and Handbooks;N
Yes	By completing the applic	Agree	NOW Learning Room;Dro
Yes	It was a lot easier the mc	Strongly agree	Guides and Handbooks;N
Yes	I was unaware of it to be	Strongly Disagree	Workshops;Drop-in sessi
Yes	Greatly	Strongly agree	NOW Learning Room;Wc
Yes	it has made me realize th	Strongly agree	Guides and Handbooks;D
Yes	Absolutely it's made me	Strongly agree	NOW Learning Room;MS
Yes	It is thoughtful process w	Strongly agree	Drop-in sessions;MS Tea
Yes	I have gradually apprecia	Agree	NOW Learning Room;Dro
Yes	So much support from th	Agree	Guides and Handbooks;N
Yes	No change	Agree	Guides and Handbooks;D
No	no	Strongly Disagree	MS Teams;NOW Learning
Yes	That it was a lot bigger u	Agree	Drop-in sessions;Worksh
Yes	Better understanding of	Agree	NOW Learning Room;Dro
Yes	I am now aware of furth	Agree	Drop-in sessions;Worksh
Yes	It felt like a massive hill t	Strongly agree	NOW Learning Room;MS
Yes	At first, I was dreading it	Agree	NOW Learning Room;MS
No	I am relieved it's over... i	Agree	Workshops;NOW Learnin
Yes	No change	Agree	NOW Learning Room;Gu

To what extent do you agree since completing a category Thank you again for comments	
Strongly Agree	Become a reviewer;
Strongly Agree	Have offered all of the at Fantastic supportive experience that has helped inspire me
Agree	Encouraging my colleague It was a pleasant experience
Agree	Shared my Fellowship story;
Strongly Agree	Become a reviewer;Supp Fantastic experience - Kate and Laura thank you so much fo
Strongly Agree	Supported others with their submission;
Strongly Agree	Shared my Fellowship story;
Strongly Agree	Shared my Fellowship st; Thanks so much all for the support, and the great online spa
Strongly Agree	Shared my Fellowship st; It has been an extremely valuable experience to me - thank
Strongly Agree	Shared my Fellowship st; Thank you for your kind support.
Agree	Supported others with th I would like to receive the news about the further applicati
Agree	I am considering Senior Fellowship;
Agree	Newsletters for HEA;
Agree	suggested fellowship to ; Thank you!
Strongly Agree	Become a reviewer; Kate and Laura, you are both awesome and I am not sure Fe
Strongly Agree	Shared my Fellowship story;
Agree	Become a reviewer;Supported others with their submission;
Strongly Agree	Planning to support othe Laura and Kate did an excellent job helping me. The drop-in
Agree	talked to colleagues about it;
Strongly Agree	Become a reviewer;Supp Thanks for your support and motivation. It is hugely valued
Agree	None of the above; A very positive experience. Just wanted to say thank you fo
Agree	Continued engagement has not been possible due to the fractional nature of my pos
Agree	I have acted as a review; KC is incredibly supportive and generous with her time.
Strongly Agree	Supported others with th N/A
Strongly Agree	Not at this stage - but ha The support from both Kate and Laura have been invaluable
Agree	Shared my Fellowship st; It was a rewarding experience
Strongly Agree	I've just completed it but I do believe a guide or book on how to write a fellowship cl;
Strongly Agree	Become a reviewer; Laura and Kate are great coaches and are always on hand fo
Strongly Agree	Supported others with th Supportive and Knowledgeable team
Strongly Agree	Only recently completed The team that have supported my fellowship process have l
Strongly Agree	Shared my Fellowship story;
Agree	Shared my Fellowship story;
Agree	not long enough yet to do anything else;
Strongly Agree	I have discussed what it's n/a
Strongly Agree	Become a reviewer;
Strongly Agree	Not had opportunity yet;
Strongly Agree	N/A; Thank you so much! I started my AFHEA journey several year
Strongly Agree	Supported others with their submission;
Strongly Agree	*; It's exhausting and I was reluctant to send work in to be rev
Agree	none;

ou taking the time to do this. Please add any additional comments about your Fellowship experience with
to work towards my Prof doc in Education Studies and once I have evidence of sustained impact to work

ance and events you run on MS Teams. I especially appreciate that there are always updates for me to re:

ons and relating requirements. As sometimes, I received emails or saw some news, but I am not sure wh

r the timely and encouraging support UI have received throughout the processes, especially from Laura

and directly impacted my success in achieving AFHEA recognition. With their support and motivation I

aim is needed. Not for the usual reasons of providing case studies, because I truly believe its difficult to j
or help and advice. Incredibly knowledgable and always happy to help. Very approachable and a huge as

been excellent. At times in this survey I have answered disagree to certain things - for example whether

ars ago at a different institution and I feel like I've been able to achieve it now due to the fantastic supp

: towards PFHEA within the foreseeable future And would love to continue to engage if the opportunity a

ad when I have time, but this team site does not "@mention" the team in every post, like many other CI

whether I am allowed to apply for, or whether my experience is consistent with the requirements.

provide a one size fits all example, but the resource would provide insights as to how to be more explicit

or not I have changed my teaching practice. This is not because the sessions provided haven't had a pos

PD teams do - this means I don't get loads of notifications that override my custom settings. Sounds like

t regarding ones own achievements, proper citation techniques for this type of submission, and various

sitive impact, simply that I have seen the sessions as specifically working towards the fellowship applicat

a small thing, but I really have had to leave optional Teams sites in the past because the number of @te

other questions which are usually sent on to the TILT support team. They already provide a good amount

of support and resources and it would be quite cumbersome to respond to each enquiry no matter how

ow valuable it is.